

Gravimetric Determination of Palladium(II), Copper(II) and Nickel(II), and Palladium(II), Copper(II) and Manganese(II) from Ternary Mixtures, using 2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime and 1-Hydroxy-2-acetonaphthoneoxime†

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2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime and its isomer 1-hydroxy-2-acetonaphthoneoxime have been used as reagents for the gravimetric determination of palladium(II), copper(II) and nickel(II) as well as palladium(II), copper(II) and manganese(II) from ternary mixtures. The results obtained are fairly accurate.

2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime (2-HANO), and its isomer, 1-hydroxy-2-acetonaphthoneoxime (1-HANO) have been extensively studied in these laboratories¹⁻⁷. 2-HANO gives a yellow precipitate with Pd²⁺ (pH 1.5-2.5), a buff coloured precipitate with Cu²⁺ (pH 3.5-6.0), a greenish yellow precipitate with Ni²⁺ (pH 8.0-10.0) and a dark green precipitate with Mn²⁺ (pH 8.0-10.0). Similarly, 1-HANO gives a deep yellow precipitate with Pd²⁺, grey precipitate with Cu²⁺, greenish yellow precipitate with Ni²⁺ and dark green precipitate with Mn²⁺ under similar experimental conditions. Accordingly, procedures were developed for the gravimetric determination of these metals when present either singly or in binary mixtures^{1,3,4}. The present paper deals with their determination in ternary mixtures.

2-HANO

1-HANO

Experimental

The reagents were prepared by the procedures reported earlier^{1,8}. A 1% (w/v) solution of 1-HANO in rectified spirit was used, while in case

of 2-HANO a 1% (w/v) solution was prepared in 1 : 1 aqueous ethanol. Stock solutions of copper sulphate, nickel sulphate and manganese chloride were prepared using AnalaR samples and were standardised⁹. In the case of palladium chloride, a solution was prepared by dissolving palladium chloride (Reachim, USSR) (1 g) in concentrated HCl (10 ml) and making up in a one litre standard flask, and the palladium content was determined using dimethylglyoxime⁹. Solutions for the study of interference by diverse ions were prepared such that each ml contained about 10 mg of the metal ions. In case of Au³⁺ and Pt⁴⁺ the solutions were prepared such that each ml contained about 1 mg of the metal ions. A pH of 1.5 was maintained with 2 M HCl in case of Pd²⁺. Similarly, sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer and ammonium chloride-ammonium hydroxide buffer were used to maintain the pH at 4.5 and 8.5, respectively in the cases of Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Mn²⁺. The determinations gave very good results under those pH conditions.

Determination of Pd²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ from ternary mixtures: Aliquots of the standard solutions of palladium chloride, copper sulphate and nickel sulphate were pipetted out into a clean 250 ml beaker and diluted to about 150 ml with distilled water. The pH was adjusted to 1.5 with 2 M HCl and the reagent (1-HANO or 2-HANO) was added dropwise with

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constant stirring (1 ml per mg of the metal). The precipitate was digested on a hot-water-bath for 15 min, filtered on a sintered crucible (IG-4), washed with aqueous ethanol (4:1), dried at 110-20° and weighed as $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ in case of 1-HANO and as $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in case of 2 HANO. The filtrate was concentrated to about 150 ml, a few ml of 1 N NaOH was added to neutralise the solution and copper was precipitated at pH 4.5 and weighed as $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ after digestion, washing and drying. The filtrate was concentrated again to 150 ml and nickel was precipitated at pH 8.5 and weighed as $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ after digestion, washing and drying. The gravimetric factors for Pd^{II} , Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} are 0.2099, 0.1370 and 0.1278, respectively. In case of palladium complex with 2-HANO, the gravimetric factor is 0.2028 corresponding to the formula $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Results are shown in Table 1.

Study of interference by diverse ions: Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} and Pt^{IV} did not interfere in case of Pd^{II} , but Au^{III} interfered. Similarly, Cd^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} did not interfere in case of Cu^{II} . Mn^{II} interfered in case of Ni^{II} and Ni^{II} interfered in case of Mn^{II} as both are precipitated under similar conditions. Even masking with cyanide was of no use. The interference due to Co^{II} in case of both Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} was overcome by the use of a solution of 1 M ammonium thiocyanate. Six determinations each of 10.57 mg of Pd^{II} , 10.02 mg of Cu^{II} , 11.30 mg of Ni^{II} and 11.77 mg of Mn^{II} with 1-HANO gave standard deviations of 0.05₂, 0.02₈, 0.02₈ and 0.05₆ mg, respectively; the relative mean errors being ± 0.19 , ± 0.10 , ± 0.09 and $\pm 0.25\%$, respectively. Similarly, six determinations each of 11.09 mg of Pd^{II} , 10.02 mg of Cu^{II} , 15.54 mg of Ni^{II} and 11.77 mg of Mn^{II} with 2-HANO gave standard deviations of 0.03₂, 0.04₈,

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Pd^{II} , Cu^{II} AND Ni^{II} IN TERNARY MIXTURES

Metal	Computed value (mg)		Experimental value (mg)		Error, %	
	2-HANO	1-HANO	2-HANO	1-HANO	2-HANO	1-HANO
Pd	(DMG method)					
	5.55	5.29	5.56	5.31	-0.18	+0.38
	11.09	10.57	11.10	10.54	+0.09	-0.28
	16.64	21.14	16.68	21.18	+0.24	+0.18
Cu	(Iodometric method)					
	10.02	10.02	10.00	10.04	-0.20	+0.20
	18.04	20.04	18.08	20.08	+0.22	+0.20
	24.05	30.06	24.02	30.11	-0.12	+0.16
Ni	(DMG method)					
	15.54	11.30	15.52	11.25	-0.13	-0.34
	26.64	22.60	26.72	22.50	+0.30	-0.44
	37.74	33.90	37.62	33.82	-0.32	-0.24

Determination of Pd^{II} , Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} in ternary mixtures: The procedure followed was similar as described above except that a standard solution of manganese sulphate was used in place of a standard solution of nickel sulphate in the ternary mixture. The gravimetric factor for Mn^{II} is 0.1207. Results are shown in Table 2.

0.03₇ and 0.06₈ mg, respectively; the relative mean errors being ± 0.36 , ± 0.54 , ± 0.19 and $\pm 0.08\%$, respectively.

Results and Discussion

From the Tables 1 and 2 it is evident that 5.0-25.0 mg of the metal ions can be determined

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Pd^{II} , Cu^{II} AND Mn^{II} IN TERNARY MIXTURE

Metal	Computed value (mg)		Experimental value (mg)		Error, %	
	2-HANO	1-HANO	2-HANO	1-HANO	2-HANO	1-HANO
Pd	(DMG method)					
	5.55	5.29	5.58	5.33	+0.76	+0.57
	11.09	10.57	11.12	10.63	+0.54	+0.57
	16.64	21.14	16.66	21.02	+0.12	+0.54
Cu	(Iodometric method)					
	10.02	10.02	9.98	9.99	-0.40	-0.30
	18.04	20.04	18.02	20.00	-0.22	-0.20
	24.05	30.06	24.00	30.01	+0.12	-0.16
Mn	(DMG method)					
	9.31	9.31	9.29	9.28	-0.21	-0.32
	11.77	11.77	11.71	11.82	-0.34	+0.42
	23.53	23.53	23.44	23.45	-0.38	-0.30

(with fair accuracy) with the reagents studied. The results presented are comparable to those obtained with 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-methyl-chalconeoxime⁹ in case of determination of Pd²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ in ternary mixtures. No results are available for comparison with ternary mixtures containing Pd²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Mn²⁺ as only these two reagents happen to be used for the purpose. The present study indicates that both the reagents studied are suitable for the determination of Pd²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ or Pd²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Mn²⁺ in ternary mixtures. Though 2-HANO happens to be as good as 1-HANO in its potentiality as a gravimetric reagent, 1-HANO scores over 2-HANO in view of ease in its preparation and greater stability of its alcoholic solution.

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